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Biodegradation potential of fenthion and disulfoton on inoculated biochar through alluvial Danube sediment

Snežana Maletić, Irina Jevrosimov, Marijana Kragulj Isakovski, Dragana Tamindzija, Ana Volaric, Tamara Apostolovic, and Srdjan Roncevic
University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental protection, Novi Sad, Serbia (snezana.maletic@dh.uns.ac.rs)

Increased pesticide uses over the last few decades raise a serious threat to environment, especially to the groundwater the most important drinking water resource. This work investigates the biodegradation potential of two selected organophosphorus pesticides, OPPs (fenthion and disulfoton) on Danube alluvial sediment in the presence of microbially inoculated biochar (BC). The investigated BC was produced by slow pyrolysis of the *Miscanthus giganteus* at a temperature of 400°C. *Bacillus megaterium* BD5 was isolated from the alluvial Danube sediment sample and was successfully immobilized on BC in the form of vegetative cells and endospores. The breakthrough curve of thiourea as a nonsorbing substance was symmetrical, indicating absence of physical nonequilibrium processes in porous media. In general, the results indicate that the R_d coefficient for fenthion ($R_d=30$) is higher than the R_d for disulfoton ($R_d=20$), but higher biodegradation was observed for disulfoton ($\lambda=6$) than for fenthion ($\lambda=4.5$). The highest biodegradation could be a consequence of high adsorption on BC and biosorption. Further enhancement of the biodegradation processes could be achieved by integration with bioelectrochemical remediation system, which will be done in the future experiments.

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